

Analytical Mathematical Proof Of Newton's Second Law.

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ABSTRACT.

By Newton's second law of motion, the net force acting on an object is equal to the change rate of momentum. Mathematically, this is expressed as $\vec{f} = d\vec{p}/dt \dots(i)$. Generally, according to this law a force takes time to change the velocity of the object in question. This certainly means that if a net force is exerted on an object with velocity v_i ($v_i \rightarrow$ *initial velocity*) at time t_i ($t_i \rightarrow$ *initial time = 0 units of time*), the object will attain its new velocity v_f ($v_f \rightarrow$ *final velocity*) at time t_f ($t_f \rightarrow$ *final time*) due to the net force exerted on it. And definitely, this implies that the time interval $t_f - t_i$ is greater than zero ($t_f - t_i > 0$). So if we were to generate a well-constructed mathematical proof that would verify Newton's second law such a proof has to attest that indeed $t_f - t_i > 0$. But apparently, there is no generally agreed upon mathematical proof to affirm whether Newton's second law of motion is precise or not precise. Hence, there is need for such a proof. And generating such a proof is the principal objective of this paper. So concisely, this paper seeks to verify whether Newton's second law of motion is a valid measurement of force. In this paper, I have generated an analytical mathematical proof using the method of contradiction which has clearly demonstrated that a force takes no time to change the velocity of an object. This means that the time interval $t_f - t_i$ is equal to zero. This means that Newton's second law is incorrect. Using this same proof, I have illustrated that force and energy are equal (a force is a package or unit of kinetic energy). Additionally, to confirm the validity of the proof, I have used the results of the proof to illustrate that centripetal acceleration is equal to $2\sqrt{2}v^2/\pi r$ which is equal to Newton's accepted expression v^2/r . The two are equal because the constant $2\sqrt{2}/\pi$ is equal to 0.899954085 which is approximately equal to one. Furthermore, considering the concept behind constantly accelerated motion which I have outlined in this paper, it follows that the observed motion of objects undergoing constantly accelerated motion exhibits properties of energy quantization. This shows that Newtonian mechanics is in agreement with the principle of energy quantization.

INTRODUCTION.

The concept of force is one of the most fundamental concepts in physics. This is because a force is primarily responsible for kinetic energy exchanges that occur between various objects and particles during interactions. With regard to the standard knowledge of dynamics, an object may speed up, slow down, or change direction in response to a force and presently, we have understood that all the fundamental natural phenomena such as gravity, electromagnetism and the nuclear interactions in atoms are governed by laws that are firmly based on the concept of force and energy.

With the help of the advances in the knowledge of quantum physics, we now know that the Gravitational force, Electromagnetic force and the Nuclear forces which are the Strong and Weak force are all made possible because of force carrying particles called Bosons. These particles are believed to carry force and they transmit kinetic energy. Therefore, knowing how to correctly quantify a force is very vital in as much as the study of Dynamics and Physics as a whole is concerned. This is because the correct interpretation of most basic natural phenomena entirely rests on the precise understanding and measurement of force and energy.

Intuitively, a force is a quantitative explanation of an interaction that causes a change in an objects state of motion. In modern Physics, a force is formally defined by Newton's second law of motion. Mathematically, this is signified by the mechanical equation $\vec{f} = m\vec{a} \dots(ii)$. Here we take mass to be constant as well as acceleration. Unfortunately, equation (i) and (ii) are generalizations of experience. In simpler terms, they have no derivation. And as much as my literature serves me well, there is no mathematical proof that supports the validity of equation (i) and (ii) which means these two equations might be inexact measurement of force. And if that's the case then it means that our understanding of most natural phenomena is biased. Thus, there is need for a proof in order to verify whether Newton's second law of motion is biased or not biased.

But generating such a mathematical proof may not be as easy as it may seem because of what I earlier articulated. Newton's second law has no well-established mathematical derivation. It is merely a generalization of reasoning. Though one way to prove it would be to try and check whether this dynamical law satisfies the known facts in kinematics because in principle, the laws of dynamics are the agents of the laws of kinematics. And that is the concept on which the proof provided in this paper is based.

One of the results of this proof is that force and energy are the same. This result is very significant in the sense that it has unified two highly fundamental concepts in Physics which are Kinetic Energy and Force. The unification of these two concepts is very vital because it might help us understand more on how Bosons carry force and convert it to Energy. This will in turn enhance our current understanding of the natural phenomena of action at a distance. This includes phenomena such as Magnetism, Gravity and Quantum Entanglement.

METHOD.

Introduction

Proof by Contradiction is the method used to generate the proof in this paper. In logic a proof by contradiction is a form of proof that establishes the truth or validity of a statement by first assuming that the opposite statement is true, and then shows that such an assumption leads to a contradiction with known facts. So if we have two statements, let's say A and B where by A is opposite to B. In order to prove the validity of A, we first assume that B is true. This may result in B producing undesirable results or desirable results. Producing desirable results here means the statement or preposition is in agreement with known facts. And if B produces desirable results then it means A will produce undesirable results and vice versa. This is because A is the direct opposite of B. So in either cases, the results of the assumption led to a contradicting statement which confirms either A or B to be true thereby implying that the other one is false.

Axioms

The proof provided in this paper is based on the following three axioms.

Axiom.1

For a body moving in a straight line with constant acceleration, the following four kinematic equations hold. Provided that the motion takes place in an inertia frame and the observe is in the same inertia frame of reference.

- i. $\Delta x = v_0 t + \frac{1}{2} a t^2$ (2)
- ii. $v^2 - v_0^2 = 2a\Delta x$ (3)
- iii. $\Delta x = \frac{1}{2}(v + v_0)t$ (4)
- iv. $v - v_0 = at$ (5)

Where; $\Delta x \rightarrow$ displacement, $v \rightarrow$ final velocity, $v_0 \rightarrow$ initial velocity, $a \rightarrow$ acceleration and $t \rightarrow$ time interval between v and v_0 .

Note: Both v_0 and v are far less than the speed of light in a vacuum. Thus, relativistic effects are negligible.

Axiom.2

Newton's first law of motion is true in all inertia frames of reference. Newton's first law states that a body stays at rest or moves with constant velocity in a straight line unless acted on by a force.

Axiom.3

There exists a number called an infinitesimal or immediate zero number. An immediate zero number is a member of hyperreal or non-standard numbers. This number can occur either to the

right or left of zero. And zero is the only real number with a magnitude smaller than the magnitude of the immediate zero number. A number is said to be indivisible or inseparable if it has the same magnitude as the immediate zero number.

Outline of the proof

The preposition or statement which we are proving is that a force takes time to change the velocity of an object. This statement comes as a result of Newton's second law of motion. Below is a mathematical expression of Newton's second law if we take mass and acceleration to be constant.

$$\vec{f} = \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} = \frac{m d\vec{v}}{dt} = m\vec{a} = m \left(\frac{v_f - v_i}{t_f - t_i} \right)$$

So in simpler terms, our preposition means that the time interval $t_f - t_i$ is greater than zero. But in order to prove this preposition by contradiction we need a preposition opposite to it. And the appropriate opposite preposition is that a force takes no time to change the velocity of an object. Mathematically, this implies that $t_f - t_i = 0$. This also means that the velocity of a body changes instantly in zero time when a force acts. Therefore, the action time $t_f - t_i$ is equal to zero and because of that, we are going to neglect it because if we plug it into the equation, the equation will be undefined. This plainly shows that our opposite preposition requires us to write the equation for force as follows;

$$\vec{f} = m d\vec{v} = m\Delta v = \text{impulse}$$

So now we have to prepositions as required.

Preposition.1

A force takes time to change the velocity of an object. Thus, $t_f - t_i > 0$ and $\vec{f} = \frac{m d\vec{v}}{dt}$ or $\vec{f} = m\vec{a}$.

Preposition.2

A force does not take time to change the velocity of an object. Thus, $t_f - t_i = 0$ and $\vec{f} = m d\vec{v}$ or $\vec{f} = m\Delta v$.

But what known facts are we going to use in order to verify that one preposition is true while the other one is wrong? This is where the three axioms will come into play. The three axioms shall be our known facts. We shall start by assuming that preposition.2 is true while preposition.1 is false. And then we are going to use axiom.1, axiom.2, axiom.3 and preposition.2 to derive the kinematic equations in axiom.1. The logic behind this is that if we can derive the kinematic equations in axiom.1 using preposition.2 then it means we cannot derive the kinematic equations using preposition.1. Which further means that preposition.2 is the true while preposition.1 is false.

The proof

The proof provided below is structured in a series of well-organized steps. In this proof, we are going to take gravity as our example for a force. And acceleration towards the earth's Centre due to gravity as our example of constant acceleration. We shall also take air resistance near the earth's surface to be negligible.

Step one: Assumption

Assume that proposition.2 is true while proposition.1 is false. Let us now try to derive the kinematic equations in axiom.1 by using axiom.2, axiom.3 and proposition.2.

Step two: Analysis of constantly accelerated motion.

We shall start the derivation by first analyzing the ratio $v - v_0 / t_f - t_i$ or $\Delta v / \Delta t$ from equation(5). When we analyse this ratio, we will find that so long as the equality $a = \Delta v / \Delta t$ holds, there exists the most simplified ratio for $\Delta v / \Delta t$ which we will denote be d/h such that Δv and Δt are multiples of d and h respectively. By the phrase, "most simplified ratio", I mean that either both d and h or one of the two is inseparable or indivisible. The reason I am saying that either both d and h or one of the two is indivisible is this. We know that when acceleration is constant, all values for velocity (v) and time (t) are a set of ordered pairs for $(t, v) \leftrightarrow (x, y)$ on the two dimensional Cartesian coordinate plane. (see figure 1.1 below).

Figure 1.1

So any value of $\Delta v / \Delta t$ we choose to take can be expressed in form of a simplified ratio with values of Δv and Δt which are smaller than the ones which we had in the previous ratio. And we can do the same to this simplified ratio to obtain an even more simplified ratio. We can continue doing this until we reach a point where either both Δv and Δt or one of the two becomes infinitesimally small such that we can hardly reduce further. This is the point I am calling the end point of reduction. And the values of Δv and Δt at this point are d and h respectively. And since Δv and Δt are multiples of d and h respectively, then it means

$$\frac{d}{h} = \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta t} \dots\dots(6). \text{ And thus, } \frac{d}{h} = a \dots\dots(7).$$

To give a more practical explanation of this idea, imagine a situation where by our acceleration $a = 0.5m/s^2$. Imagine also that at some time during the motion $\Delta v = 1m/s$ meaning $\Delta t = 2s$. This gives us the ratio 1/2. We can express this ratio in a more simplified ratio as shown in table 1.1 below.

Table1.1

Value of Δv when Δv is divided by n	Value of Δt when Δt is divided by n	Value of n
1	2	1
0.2	0.4	5
0.01	0.02	20
0.0002	0.0004	50
0.0000002	0.0000004	1000

Here our simplest fraction d/h would be $0.0000002/0.0000004$. Meaning that $d = 0.0000002$ and $h = 0.0000004$. Then the set(E) of ordered pairs for (x,y) would be;

$E = \{(2,1), (4 \times 10^{-1}, 2 \times 10^{-1}), (2 \times 10^{-2}, 1 \times 10^{-2}), (4 \times 10^{-4}, 2 \times 10^{-4}), (4 \times 10^{-7}, 2 \times 10^{-7}), \dots \dots \dots, (x, y)\}$. Where 1, 0.2, 0.01, 0.0002, and 0.0000002 are different consecutive values for velocity(v) corresponding to 2, 0.4, 0.02, 0.0004, and 0.0000004 as different consecutive values of time (t). In this order, we see that the ratio $\Delta v/\Delta t$ is equal to or can be expressed in its simplest form $0.0000002/0.0000004$. Therefore, the ratio $\Delta v/\Delta t$ can generally be expressed as, dn/hn . This means that,

$$\frac{\Delta v}{\Delta t} = \frac{dn}{hn} \dots\dots(8) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dn}{hn} = a \dots\dots(9).$$

Where d is a real number (because it represents velocity), h is any number greater than zero (because it represents time) and n is a whole number (because it represents the number of infinitesimal parts h or d adding up to make Δt or Δv respectively). Now if we look at equation (7) very closely,

$$\frac{d}{h} = a \dots\dots(7),$$

While also remembering our assumption that a force takes no time to change the velocity of an object. We will see that equation (7) can only be true if a force acts after a time interval h , thereby causing a change in velocity of magnitude $|d|$ in zero time. Meaning before a force acts, there will first be a change in time by a magnitude of h . Thereafter, the force will act, and the velocity will change instantly in zero time. So that,

$$\frac{\text{change in velocity}}{\text{change in time}} = \frac{d}{h} = a$$

And if we look closely at equation (9), the is equation is telling us that before every d change in velocity, first there is an h change in time. So initial velocity v_0 can only change to final velocity v_f after some time interval h provided $v_f - v_0 = d$. (remember velocity is changing in zero time). And since Δv and Δt are multiples of d and h respectively, then it follows that,

$$\frac{\Delta v}{n} = d \dots\dots\dots(10) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\Delta t}{n} = h \dots\dots\dots(11).$$

Analytically, this is the logic or principle behind constantly accelerated motion if we assume velocity to be changing in zero time.

Step three: we further analyze the motion of a body under constant acceleration, but this time in relation to gravity.

Let us now consider the vertical motion of a body(**Q**) near the surface of the Earth under the influence of gravity towards the Centre of the Earth. The body will fall from some height which we denote by Δx above the surface of the Earth. Let $\Delta x = p_k - p_0$, where $(p_0, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k)$ denotes positions of the body in motion at times $(t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$ as it falls towards the Earths centre under the influence of gravity. And let Δt denote the time taken to change velocity from initial velocity v_0 to final velocity v which we can also denote by v_n . Where, n represents the number of times the force has acted on the body (recall that by newtons first law, a body changes its state of motion only when a force acts upon it. so each time n the force acts on the body, the velocity of the body changes from v_n to v_{n+1}). Note also that Δx represents the change in position (displacement) from initial (p_0) to final position (p_k) where k is a natural number.

Also note that $(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$ are the velocities which the body will have when leaving position $(p_0, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k)$ provided $v_0 = 0 \text{ m/s}$. When we take the limits of $(v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ at times $(t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$ we have $(\frac{dx_0}{dt}, \frac{dx_1}{dt}, \frac{dx_2}{dt}, \dots, \frac{dx_n}{dt})$ as instantenous velocities. Only the numerators change because the value of dt is the same for all instantenous velocities and with that in mind, we can see that what differentiates the magnitudes of the instantenous velocities is their numerators $(dx_0, dx_1, dx_2, \dots, dx_n)$. Furthermore, It is these same numerators which change when a force acts on a body. For simplicity sake, let $dx_0 = \Delta$.

Step four: Derivation of kinematic equations.

So each time (n) the force acts on the body, the numerator of the instantenous velocity at that time (t_n) increases by the constant number (d) . Meaning when the force acts for $(0,1,2, \dots, n)$ time(s), the numerator of the instantenous velocity $(\frac{dx_0}{dt}, \frac{dx_1}{dt}, \frac{dx_2}{dt}, \dots, \frac{dx_n}{dt})$ becomes $(\Delta, \Delta + d, \Delta + 2d, \dots, \Delta + nd)$ respectively. Implying that when velocity is equal to $(v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, then dx_0 will be equal to Δ while $dx_1, dx_2,$ and dx_n will be equal to $\Delta + d, \Delta + 2d,$ and $\Delta + nd$ respectively. Since a force doesn't take time to produce effect, (that's according to our contradicting statement) the velocity of the body will be changing from initial

velocity v_n to final velocity v_{n+1} there and then (instantly) in zero time each time (n) the force acts and thereafter continue moving with velocity v_{n+1} until the force acts again after some time h .

Below is **Figure 1.2** summarizing the motion of body **Q**.

As a result, the body will be undergoing the following displacements(see below) after some time (Δt), where $\Delta t \geq h$.

Between; p_0 and $p_1 = v_0h + v_1h = \frac{\Delta.h}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+d)}{dt}$

$$p_0 \text{ and } p_2 = v_0h + v_1h + v_2h = \frac{\Delta.h}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+d)}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+2d)}{dt}$$

$$p_0 \text{ and } p_3 = v_0h + v_1h + v_2h + v_3h = \frac{\Delta.h}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+d)}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+2d)}{dt} + \frac{h.(\Delta+3d)}{dt}$$

$$p_0 \text{ and } p_k = v_0h + \dots + h.(v_{n-1}) = \frac{h.\Delta}{dt} + \dots + \frac{h.[\Delta+(n-1)d]}{dt}$$

Hence,

$$\Delta x = p_k - p_0 = h \left[\frac{\Delta}{dt} + \dots + \frac{\Delta+nd}{dt} \right] \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

$$\Delta x = p_k - p_0 = h(v_0 + \dots + v_{n-1}) \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

Coincidentally, the coefficients of d ($0,1,2, \dots, n$) in equation (c2) are forming an arithmetic sequence whose common difference is one, and the first term is zero. This is because $n \geq 0$ and $d > 0$ always. Therefore, by try and error method equation (c2) can be written in the following manner.

$$\Delta x = h \left(\frac{n.\Delta}{dt} + \frac{s_n.d}{dt} \right) \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

Where s_n is the expression for the sum of an arithmetic sequence. Note that the n in s_n denotes the number of times the force has acted. Now we know that

$$s_n = \frac{n}{2} [2a + (n - 1)y]$$

Where; $y \rightarrow$ common difference which is equal to one in our case.

$a \rightarrow$ first term which is equal to zero in our case.

$n \rightarrow$ number of times the force has acted which is equal to n in our case.

Thus, $s_n = \frac{n}{2} [2a + (n - 1)y]$ yields,

$$= \frac{n}{2} [2 \times 0 + (n - 1) \times 1]$$

$$= \frac{n}{2} (n - 1)$$

$$s_n = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$$

When we replace this expression for s_n into equation (14), we get

$$\Delta x = h \left[\frac{n\Delta}{dt} + \frac{n(n-1)d}{2dt} \right] \dots\dots\dots(15).$$

But our analyses is also telling us that;

$$v_1 - v_o = ah \dots\dots\dots(16), \text{ where } a = \text{acceleration}$$

$$\Delta t = nh \dots\dots\dots(17),$$

$$v_n - v_o = a\Delta t \dots\dots\dots(18),$$

$$v_1 - v_o = \frac{d}{dt} \dots\dots\dots(19), \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{\Delta}{dt} = v_o \dots\dots\dots(20)$$

hold for $\sum \vec{f} = m\Delta\vec{v}$.

When we replace v_o from equation (20) into equation (15), we get

$$\Delta x = h \left[nv_o + \frac{n(n-1)d}{2dt} \right] \dots\dots\dots(21)$$

Let us now replace $v_1 - v_o$ from equation (19) into equation (21). This yields,

$$\Delta x = h \left[nv_o + \frac{n(n-1)(v_1 - v_o)}{2} \right] \dots\dots\dots(22). \text{ And when we replace } \frac{\Delta t}{n} \text{ from}$$

equation (17) into equation (21), we get,

$$\Delta x = \frac{\Delta t}{n} \left[nv_o + \frac{n(n-1)(v_1 - v_o)}{2} \right] \dots\dots\dots(23),$$

When we open the square blankets, we get,

$$\Delta x = v_o\Delta t + \frac{n(n-1)(v_1 - v_o)\Delta t}{2} \dots\dots\dots(23),$$

And now, when we replace ah from equation (16) into equation (23), we get

$$\Delta x = v_o \Delta t + \frac{(n-1)(ah)\Delta t}{2} \dots\dots\dots(24),$$

Let us once more replace $\frac{\Delta t}{n}$ from equation (17) into equation (23), we get

$$\Delta x = v_o \Delta t + \frac{(n-1)a\Delta t^2}{2n} \dots\dots\dots(25),$$

$$\Delta x = v_o \Delta t + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n-1}{n} \right) a \Delta t^2 \dots\dots\dots(25),$$

Now let $G = \frac{n-1}{n}$. Thus, equation (25) becomes,

$$\Delta x = v_o \Delta t + \frac{Ga\Delta t^2}{2} \dots\dots\dots(26).$$

If we plug in several different values of n into G , we will see that as n increases without bound, G approaches the number one. Or in other words let me say that the limit of G as n approaches infinity is equal to one. (see table1.0 below for different values G and n).

Table1.0

Value of n	Value of $\frac{n-1}{n}$
1	0
5	0.8
20	0.95
100	0.99
500	0.998
1000	0.999

But when you observe how objects fall under the influence of gravity, you will notice that an object with $v_o = 0m/s$ that stays in motion for atleast less than half a second, exhibits changes in velocity that are approximately more than 10 times (n) which implies that h is small. Now since h is small, then most values of Δt which we calculate must come has a result of $n > 5$ and hence, we conclude that G is approximately equal to one. Thus, equation (26) becomes,

$$\Delta x = v_o \Delta t + \frac{a\Delta t^2}{2} \dots\dots\dots(27).$$

And replacing the expression for Δt from equation (18) into equation (27), we get

$$\Delta x = \left(\frac{v_n - v_o}{a} \right) v_o + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v_n - v_o}{a} \right)^2 a \dots\dots\dots(28), \text{ simplifying this}$$

expression yields,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{v_n v_o - v_o^2}{a} + \frac{(v_n - v_o)^2}{2a} \\ &= \frac{2v_o v_n - 2v_o^2 + v_n^2 - 2v_o v_n + v_o^2}{2a} \\ &= \frac{2v_o v_n - 2v_o v_n - 2v_o^2 + v_o^2 + v_n^2}{2a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\Delta x}{1} = \frac{v_n^2 - v_o^2}{2a} \quad \text{when we cross multiply, we get}$$

$$v_n^2 - v_o^2 = 2\Delta x \cdot a$$

$$v_n^2 = v_o^2 + 2\Delta x \cdot a \quad \dots\dots\dots(29).$$

But equation (29) can also be written as, (when we make Δx the subject of the formula)

$$\Delta x = \frac{v_n^2 - v_o^2}{2a} = \frac{(v_n - v_o)(v_n + v_o)}{2a} \quad \dots\dots\dots(30). \quad \text{Which also implies;}$$

$$\Delta x = \frac{(v_n - v_o)(v_n + v_o)}{2} \times \frac{1}{a} \quad \dots\dots\dots(31).$$

Let us get $\frac{v_n - v_o}{\Delta t}$ from equation (18) and replace it with a in equation (31). This yields,

$$\Delta x = \frac{(v_n - v_o)(v_n + v_o)}{2} \times \frac{\Delta t}{v_n - v_o} \quad \dots\dots\dots(32).$$

$$\Delta x = \frac{(v_n - v_o)(v_n + v_o)\Delta t}{2(v_n - v_o)} \quad \dots\dots\dots(32).$$

The “ $v_n - v_o$ ” terms cancel out, and we remain with

$$\Delta x = \frac{(v_n + v_o)\Delta t}{2} \quad \dots\dots\dots(33).$$

Step five: Concluding statement.

So far, from the analysis that we have done, it shows that preposition.1 can derive the equations (2), (3), (4), and (5) as equation (27), (29), (33), and (18) respectively. Implying that the equation $\sum \vec{f} = m\Delta\vec{v}$ conceptually satisfies the equations (5), (2), (3), and (4) for constant acceleration. Therefore, by contradiction, it follows that the equation $\sum \vec{f} = m\vec{a}$ does not conceptually satisfy equation (5), (2), (3), and (4) for constant acceleration. This means preposition.2 is false and hence, the proof.

This signifies that a force must be measured by the formula $\sum \vec{f} = m\Delta\vec{v}$ and not by the formula $\sum \vec{f} = m\vec{a}$. And this also means that

$$\sum \vec{f} = m\Delta\vec{v} = \text{impulse} = \int_{t_o}^{t_z} (ma)dt.$$

And that the formula $\sum \vec{f} = m\vec{a}$ gives the value of the force acting per unit time. This means

$$ma = \text{mass} \times \text{acceleration} = \frac{f}{\Delta t} = \frac{\text{force}}{\text{change in time}}$$

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The following are the results of the proof.

- A. The work done-kinetic energy theorem breaks down.
- B. The formula for centripetal acceleration is revised.
- C. Newtonian Mechanics becomes in tune with the theory of energy quantization.

A. The work done-kinetic energy theorem breaks down.

By definition, kinetic energy ($K.E$) is the energy possessed by a body due to its motion (velocity). From, a conceptual point of view of this quantity, any body that has velocity (either linear or angular velocity) has kinetic energy. Formally, the work done (w) by a constant force (\vec{f}) is considered to be the measure of kinetic energy. Work done by a constant force (\vec{f}) is defined as the product of the component of the force in the direction of the displacement (\vec{s}) and the magnitude of the displacement.

$$\text{work done} = (f \cos \theta).s,$$

Where θ is the angle between (\vec{f}) and (\vec{s}). For constant acceleration,

$$|\vec{f}| = ma = m \left(\frac{v_n - v_o}{\Delta t} \right) \dots\dots\dots (a_1) \text{ and,}$$

$$|\vec{s}| = \frac{v_n^2 - v_o^2}{2a} \dots\dots\dots (a_2).$$

Hence,

$$\Delta K.E = |\vec{f}|.|\vec{s}|.$$

$$\Delta K.E = \frac{1}{2}m(v_n^2 - v_o^2).$$

$$K.E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2.$$

By virtue of equation (a_1) and (a_2), the distance $|\vec{s}|$ is considered to be the distance between position p_o and position p_k . Meaning when the force (\vec{f}) acts on the body, the velocity of the body will not change (from v_o to v_n) there and then at p_o in zero time, but it will rather change across the displacement (\vec{s}). That's what equation (a_1) and (a_2) implies. Let us now analyze **Figure1.2** on the next page once more and see the results which the work done-kinetic energy theory would produce if we take force to be equal to impulse

Figure 1.2

Assume a force (\vec{f}_1) acts on the body while it is at position p_0 with $v_0 = 0 \text{ m/s}$, the body will change velocity there and then at position p_1 from v_0 to v_1 such that the displacement $|\vec{s}_1|$ within this time interval ($\Delta t = 0 \text{ units of time}$) is zero. Hence, if we apply the work done-kinetic energy theory, we will see that;

$$K.E = |\vec{f}_1| \cdot |\vec{s}_1| = (f_1 \cos \theta) \times s_1 = (F_1 \cos \theta) \times 0 = 0 \text{ units.}$$

And we will also see that the total force ($\sum \vec{f}$) that will act on the body from position p_0 to p_k is the summation of the forces (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) that acted at time (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n). While the total distance ($\sum \vec{s}$) covered by the body in order for the body to change velocity from v_{n-1} to v_n when the force acted on the body at times (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n) will be given by the summation of the zero distances (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n). So we have,

$$\sum \vec{f} = n f_1 \text{ and } \sum \vec{s} = 0 \text{ units.}$$

Note that $f_1 = f_n$ and $s_n = 0$. Where $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n$. Therefore, the total kinetic energy ($\sum K.E$), is equal to zero.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum K.E &= \sum \vec{f} \cos \theta \times \sum \vec{s} \text{ (The cross sign } \times \text{ is for multiplication not vector cross product)} \\ &= n f_1 \cos \theta \times 0 \\ &= 0 \text{ units.} \end{aligned}$$

And consequently, the work done kinetic energy theorem breaks down. So how do we measure kinetic energy now? Let's us recall that conceptually, any object that has kinetic energy (velocity) has the ability to cause a force. Thus, intuitively kinetic energy is the ability to cause a force (not ability to do work) and vice versa a force is a package of kinetic energy. To add more meaning to this definition, let us imagine a body D_1 with mass M_1 moving with uniform velocity v_a . When we apply the force-impulse theorem, body D_1 has the ability to cause a force f_c due to its velocity v_a where $f_c = M_1 v_a$. This signifies that kinetic energy is equal to present day momentum. Which means energy is a vector quantity and that force (a pack of energy) is also energy. And it follows that,

$$\text{Mass} \times \text{acceleration} = \text{power} = \text{energy per unit time.}$$

Note: The conservation of the quantity “Newtonian force x displacement” still holds. And the current definition, work done still remains.

A. The formula for centripetal acceleration is revised.

The current formula (34) for centripetal acceleration was derivation by the physicist, Isaac Newton. Below is the formula;

$$\text{centripetal acceleration } (a_c) = \frac{\text{linear velocity of the body squared } (v^2)}{\text{radius of the circle } (r)}$$

$$a_c = \frac{v^2}{r} \dots\dots\dots (34).$$

But when we take force to be equal to impulse, this formula changes. let us derive the formula for centripetal acceleration. To help us in our analysis and derivation, let us see **Figure1.3** below.

Figure 1.3

When we look at **Figure1.3**, its shows a body of mass M moving with constant velocity v about a fixed point O around a circle with radius r . When the particle is at point A , all its velocity is along the y -axis. It has no velocity in the x -axis at point A . But when it reaches point B , it has lost all its velocity in the y -axis, and gained exactly the same velocity it has lost in the y -axis in the x -axis. So from point A to B a force of $f_x = Mv$ has acted in the x -axis and a force of $f_y = Mv$ has acted in the y -axis. Using pythagoras theorem, we see that the resultant force f_r of the two forces f_x and f_y is given by;

$$f_r = \sqrt{f_x^2 + f_y^2}$$

And the direction of f_r is towards the

center because $f_x = f_y$ and hence, the angle θ between f_r and f_y is equal to 45° .

Now we know that $f_y = f_x$ so,

$$\begin{aligned} f_r &= \sqrt{(Mv)^2 + (Mv)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{2(Mv)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{2}Mv \end{aligned}$$

Carefully observing this motion, we see that this all arrangement is taking place when the particle moves from B to C, C to D and from D to A. Meaning, this arrangement is happening four times before the particle completes one revolution. So for every complete revolution the force f_r is acting four times. Thus, for one complete revolution the total force f_T is given by;

$$\begin{aligned} f_T &= f_r \times 4 \\ &= 4\sqrt{2}Mv \end{aligned}$$

And we know that;

$$Ma_c = \frac{f}{\Delta t}$$

Where $f = f_T$, Δt is the time taken for one complete revolution which is the period given by the formular;

$T = \frac{2\pi r}{v}$, a_c is centripetal acceleration and M is the mass of the particle. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} Ma_c &= 4\sqrt{2}Mv \div \frac{2\pi r}{v} \\ &= \frac{4\sqrt{2}Mv}{1} \times \frac{v}{2\pi r} \\ Ma_c &= \frac{2\sqrt{2}Mv^2}{\pi r} \end{aligned}$$

When we multiply both sides by $\frac{1}{M}$, we remain with

$$a_c = \frac{2\sqrt{2}v^2}{\pi r} \dots\dots\dots (35)$$

Thus, we see that equation (34) is not equal to equation (35) because of the constant $\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi}$.

But $\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} = 0.899954085$ which is approximately equal to one, and that is why equation (34) for Isaac Newton works. To sum up, equation (34) has been revised as equation (35) because of the force-impulse theorem.

B. Newtonian mechanics becomes is in tune with the theory of energy quantization.

When we consider constant acceleration from the theoretical point of view outlined in this paper (Step two of the proof), we see that kinetic energy is given in packages (It is also lost in packages) or let me borrow the word “quanta” of energy in a form we presently call impulse. Even if it’s not constant acceleration, so long as the impulse-force-package of energy theorem holds, every change in velocity comes as a result of a body receiving a package of kinetic energy. From equation (5), (Part two of the proof) we have;

$$d \rightarrow \text{very small change in velocity and } h \rightarrow \text{very small change in time}$$

Thus,

$$\text{Mass x small change in velocity} = md = \text{force (package of energy)}$$

Here “*md*” represents the indivisible and discrete quantity of energy which is in line with the postulate by Max Planck(1857-1947) that;

“Energy exchanges between matter and radiation do not take place in a continuous manner, but by discrete and indivisible quantities or quanta of energy”. (Messiah, 1967 page No.10).

This also shows that Newtonian mechanics is in agreement with the principle of energy quantization.

Photoelectric effect explained.

According to classical wave theory, the frequency of a wave is the number of complete waves passing a particular point in space per unit time. So if we accept Einstein’s postulate that light is not just a wave but it can also be considered to be made up of clumps or packs of energy called Photons. Then it follows that we can redefine the frequency of a wave of light in terms of discrete energy packs in order to account for its particle nature. We shall redefine frequency as follows,

Frequency of an electromagnetic wave is the number of discrete energy clumps (photons) passing a particular point in space per unit time.

$$\text{frequency} = \frac{\text{number of photons}}{\text{time}}$$

$$f = \frac{n(m\Delta v)}{\Delta t} \dots\dots\dots(36).$$

So for a wave of light, the discrete energy pack is equal to the energy of a single photon. Following the results of the proof, we know that energy is equal to momentum. So the energy of a single photon is equal to its momentum (p). And the momentum (p) of a single photon is given by;

$$p = \frac{h}{\lambda} \dots\dots\dots(37), \text{ where } p \rightarrow \text{momentum, } h \rightarrow \text{plancks constant and } \lambda \rightarrow \text{wave length.}$$

So now equation (36) becomes

$$f = \frac{n}{\Delta t} \times p$$

$$f = \frac{n}{\Delta t} \times \frac{h}{\lambda}$$

$$f = \frac{nh}{\Delta t \lambda} \dots\dots\dots(38)$$

But we know that the frequency of a wave is given by its velocity divided by its wave length. So equation (15) becomes

$$\frac{c}{\lambda} = \frac{nh}{\Delta t \lambda}$$

$$c = \frac{nh}{\Delta t} \dots\dots\dots (39)$$

The letter “c” is the speed of light.

So for one photon (n=1) to pass a particular point in space, an interval (Δt) of time passes. This means $\Delta t = h/c \dots\dots\dots(40)$. Let us now turn our attention to the electron. For a particle such as an electron, we can picture it as being at a distance *x* away from the nucleus. The force which holds the electron to the nucleus is the electromagnetic force. So for an electron to be ejected from the atom, it has to overcome the electromagnetic force. And since the electromagnetic force field is a solenoidal vector field, it vanishes at a particular distance (*D*) from the nucleus. So for the electron to escape from the atom, it has to first gain kinetic energy which will make it cover

the distance $r = D - x$ as illustrated in the diagram below.

Kinetic energy of emitted electron and physical meaning of Planck's constant.

The kinetic energy which the electron will receive when it is at a distance D from the nucleus is the kinetic energy which it will have when it is ejected. The energy from the wave of light come in packs. So the electron will be receiving energy per unit time Δt . The energy which will make the electron to make a displacement r away from the nucleus is the energy we shall call threshold energy (E_t). So in simpler terms work has to be done on the Electron in order for it to undergo the displacement r . Mathematically, this threshold work (w_t) which has to be done on the electron can be expressed as follows,

$$\text{Threshold work} = \frac{E_t}{\Delta t} \times r$$

$$w_t = \frac{E_t}{\Delta t} \times r \dots\dots\dots(41)$$

Now let us recall that the electromagnetic force is a conservative force just like gravity. Thus every point away from the source (nucleus) is associated with a specific acceleration. So for a particle with mass such as an electron, every point along the distance r is associated with a force per unit time. This is because,

$$\text{acceleration} = \frac{\text{change in velocity}}{\text{change in time}}$$

$$\text{mass} \times \text{acceleration} = \frac{\text{mass} \times \text{change in velocity}}{\text{change in time}}$$

$$\text{mass} \times \text{acceleration} = \frac{\text{force}}{\text{change in time}} = \frac{\text{energy}}{\text{change in time}}$$

But a force per unit time is frequency. So every point away from the nucleus is associated with a particular frequency. This implies that for the electron to undergo the displacement r , it has to overcome all the frequencies along its path. So the frequency which the electron has to overcome

is the sum total of all the frequencies along its path. We shall denote this total frequency by f_s . Looking at equation (17), this means,

$$w_t = \frac{E_t}{\Delta t} \times r = f_s \times r \dots\dots\dots(42).$$

Now let us recall that Max Planck in 1900 found that the threshold work done (w_t) is equal to hf . Where h is Planck's constant and f is frequency of incident light. This means that $w_t = hc/\lambda$. Where c/λ is the frequency of incident light. Therefore,

$$f_s \times r = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \dots\dots\dots(43).$$

In equation (19) above, both f_s and c/λ represent frequency. Which means r and h represent the same quantity. But we know that r represents distance, which clearly shows that h also represents distance. So from equation (19), we see that Planck's constant is the distance from the initial position of the electron to the point where the field of force of the nucleus vanishes. This is the physical meaning behind Planck's constant. Equation (19) is also telling us that the kinetic energy of the ejected electron depends on the frequency of the incident photon. Mathematically, this can be expressed as follows.

$$E_e = p_i - p_t$$

Where E_e is the kinetic energy of ejected electron, p_i is the momentum of incident photon and p_t is the threshold momentum (threshold energy). Thus,

$$E_e = \frac{h}{c} \times (f_i - f_t) \dots\dots\dots(44).$$

Intensity and number of ejected electrons.

So far we have illustrated why there is a threshold frequency below which no emission of electrons take place and also why the kinetic energy of ejected electrons depend on the frequency of the radiation. Now let's see why the number of ejected electrons depend on the intensity of the radiation and why electrons start emitting immediately the light shines on the metal surface with no detectable time delay.

Intensity is the number of complete waves per unit time and area. Here the number of complete waves corresponds to the number of electrons. Thus intensity (I), can be expressed as follows.

$$I = \frac{\text{Number of electrons}}{\text{change in time} \times \text{area}}$$

$$I = \frac{\text{number of electrons}}{\Delta t \times A}$$

$$\text{number of electrons} = I \times \Delta t \times A$$

$$n \times \frac{h}{\lambda} = I \times \Delta t \times A$$

$$n = \frac{I \times \Delta t \times A \times \lambda}{h}$$

$$n = \frac{I \times A \times \lambda}{c}$$

$$n = I \times A \times f$$

number of electrons = intensity × area × frequency

So if we keep frequency and area constant, the number of ejected Photons is directly proportional to intensity.

Why no detectable time delay.

From equation (39) when n=1,

$$\Delta t = \frac{h}{c} \dots\dots\dots(45).$$

The time interval Δt is the time taken for the electron to cover the distance r . We can see that this time interval is extremely small that is why it is not observed. So it appears like the electrons are emitted in zero time. This is why there is no detectable time.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the proof, it has been clearly shown that the force-impulse-momentum-energy theorem is a powerful theoretical tool which can produce tremendous results in the field of science. So in conclusion, I would like to request every caring scientist out there to take this theory further and more particularly to revise electromagnetism using this theorem.

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